
The Traditional performance of the Pañcamahāyajñas in Assamese society as Reflected in the Dharmasūtras : An Observation

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ABSTRACT

The Dharmasūtras are the supplements of the *Kalpavedāṅga*, the ritual expositions of the Vedic literature, written in the *sūtra* style and dealing with the *dharma*. The word *dharma* indicates the meaning of law, justice, religion, duty, virtue, etc. The source of *dharma*, the duties of the four āśramas, various types of saṁskāras, viz., *upanayana*, *vivāha*, etc., are the basic subject-matters of the Dharmasūtras. These are considered as the compendium of Indian cultural heritage, where the socio-religious performances and traditional activities of the then Indians are reflected.

Among various topics of the *Dharmasūtra*, the Pañcamahāyajñas are the compulsory duties of a *gṛhastha* or householder to be performed everyday. These Pañcamahāyajñas are viz., Brahmajajña, Devayajña, Bhūtayajña, Pitṛyajña and Manuṣyajajña. The Brahmajajña is the sacrifice to the Brahman or the study of Vedic text; the Devayajña is the sacrifice to the Gods; the Bhūtayajña, which means the sacrifice to the other created beings; the Pitṛyajña, i.e., the sacrifice to the forefathers, and lastly the Manuṣyajajña or Nṛyajña is the sacrifice to fellow human being. The performance of these five great sacrifices is a part of the most important socio-religious duty of each householder to be performed everyday, although in reality they consist only in small offerings and a few, simple ceremonies. Here, in the present research paper, it is focused on the relevant and impact of the Pañcamahāyajñas as the socio-religious performance of a householder in Assamese society with an analytical point of view. The present research paper is an humble attempt to observe the concept of each of the five great sacrifices as enjoined in the four principal Dharmasūtras, viz., the *Vasiṣṭhadharmasūtra*, the *Baudhāyanadharmasūtra*, the *Āpastambadharmasūtra* and the *Gautamadharmasūtra*, which generates the interest for the further depth study on traditional knowledge of ancient India.

Key words- *dharmasūtra*, *gṛhastha*, *pañcamahāyajña*, *sacrifice*, *socio-religious performance*.

INTRODUCTION

The Ancient Indian cultural heritage and traditional performances are significantly depicted in the Vedic literary works. The Vedic literature includes the four Vedas and the six Vedāngas, the supplementary texts, which are very important to the better understanding of the Vedas. Without the knowledge of the Śṛvedāngas, the six limbs of the *Veda*, viz. *Śikṣā* (Phonetics), *Kalpa* (Science detailing Vedic rituals and disciplines), *Nirukta* (Etymology), *Vyākaraṇa* (Grammar), *Chandas* (Meters) and *Jyotiṣa* (Astronomy), one cannot achieve the proper meaning of Vedic concepts reflected in the Vedas. Among them, the *Kalpavedāṅga* is called as the hand of the *Vedapuruṣa*,¹ which deal with the Vedic sacrificial rituals, household ceremonies, customary laws, etc. Again, it is primarily concerned with systematic account of all the Vedic sacrifices and simply records the rituals and traditions existing in their respective schools of the four Vedas. Basically, the whole *Kalpavedāṅga* literature comprises four parts, viz. *Śrauta*, *Gṛhya*, *Dharma* and *Śulva*, which are framed in the form of sūtras, i.e. the technical maxim rule of writing style. The Śrautasūtras explain in detail about the great Vedic sacrifices known as Śrautayajñas, which are already found in the *Brāhmaṇic* literature. But, all the sacrifices described in the Śrautasūtras are not traceable to the Brāhmaṇas. The Gṛhyasūtras chiefly deal with the household ceremonies, i.e. marriage, *upanayana*, etc. Again, the Dharmasūtras put up with the social usage, customary laws and also the household ceremonies. Again, the Śulvasūtras consist of the rules for the measurement and construction of the fire-alters and sacrificial sheds, etc., are closely connected with the great Śrautayajñas. The Gṛhyasūtras are generally preceded by the Śrautasūtras of the same school. It presupposes the sacrificial knowledge of their respective schools. The main difference between the Śrautasūtras and the Gṛhyasūtras consist in the fact that the Śrautasūtras describe the sacrifices prescribed for those Āryans only, who have set up the three sacred fires, i.e. for an *Āhitāgni*. On the other hand, the Gṛhyasūtras describe the household ceremonies of daily life, which can be performed with the single *Gṛhya* fire. Another distinction is found in case of the number of priests. Sixteen priests are required for the performance of the *Śrauta* sacrifices, whereas the *Gṛhya* rites can be performed by the householder himself, or by anyone of his representatives. In various types of Śrauta sacrifices, the offering of *Soma* is prominent; on the other hand, it is absolutely unconnected with *gṛhya* rites. Again, it is noteworthy that the Gṛhyasūtras and the Dharmasūtras define the household ceremonies of daily life as well as the social practices, which can be performed by the householder (*grhastha*) himself. The Dharmasūtras set down the rules and regulations as the guidance for the social and spiritual perspective as well as the rights and duties of different classes of society during their different stages of life. But, the Gṛhyasūtras cope with the rituals and customary traditions of the domestic life to be performed by an individual. Thus, it is clear that, although several topics are common to both, but, the Dharmasūtras cover a wide range of scope of the subject matter than the Gṛhyasūtras.

The Dharmasūtras have a great importance in the Vedic literature, especially in the *Kalpavedāṅga* literature. The subject-matter of the Dharmasūtras includes various aspects of social, economic, political, religious and philosophical deeds. Usually, the term *dharma* means religion, law, usage, practice, custom, virtue, duty, right, justice, morality, etc.² The word *dharma* is definitely related to *Karman*, i.e. action or duty. As the best creation of the cosmos, human beings are bound to maintain the social responsibility to all beings. Although, the performance of the sacrificial rites in the early Vedic period is the familiar meaning of the word *dharma*, it, thereby signifies the duties and responsibilities of the people. As because, the Vedic sacrifices are directly related to the action. Every good action performed with selfless spirit should be taken as covered by the term *yajña*, i.e. sacrifice. Again the term *sūtra* indicates an aphorism or a concise technical sentence used as a dedicatory rule regarding the writing style.³ Thus, the Dharmasūtras, the *sūtra* type of literary work on *dharma*, denote such kind of work, which discusses the rules for the domestic rituals and conventional customs. P.V. Kane states that the later rules contained in the Dharmasūtras and other works on Dharmasūtras had their roots deep down in the most ancient Vedic tradition and the authors of the Dharmasūtras were quite justified in looking up to the Vedas as a source of *Dharma*.⁴ Sometimes, the Dharmasūtras are also called the Smārtasūtras as they connected with the *Smṛti* literature and in the later period it led to the Dharmasāstras, the Law Books. The Dharmasūtras nowhere claim to deal with *dharma* in its entirety, and openly declare that they are going to expound *Smārta Dharma* or *Sāmayāchārika Dharma*.⁵ The concept of *Dharma* reflected in the Dharmasūtras are based on the *Smārta Dharma*, the established traditions and the *Sāmayācārika Dharma*,⁶ the conservative practices.

The topics of the Dharmasūtras may be largely classified into three broad categories, i.e. *Varṇadharmā* (duties of four castes), *Āśramadharmā* (duties of four āśramas) and *Naimittikadharmā* (casual duties or the performances of various sacraments).⁷ The largest portion of the Dharmasūtras is covered by the subject of *Āśramadharmā*. The Dharmasūtras explain the detail knowledge of sacrificial rites and duties in a systematic way to be performed by the people of four castes (*caturvarṇas*, i.e. *Brāhmaṇa*, *Kṣetriya*, *Vaiśya* and *Śūdra*) in their four stages of human life (*caturāśramas*, i.e. *Brāhamacārya*, *Gārhasthya*, *Vānaprastha* and *Sannyāsa*). In the *Dharmasūtra* literature,⁸ the four stages of a human life are enumerated as, *Brahmacārin*, the student; *Grhastha*, the householder; *Bhikṣu* or *Paribrājaka*, the wandering ascetic and *Vaikhānasa* or *Vānaprastha*, the forest hermit. According to the ancient Indian tradition, every stage of an individual life has their significance and importance for performing different rituals and duties. Among the four stages, the householder's life has been defined as the source of other three stages; because excluding it, the other three stages cannot fulfil any offspring.⁹ The householders are expected to follow all the rules and regulations as well as moral excellences that have the responsibilities for the growth of the society.

During the Vedic civilization, the religious aspects are noticed in terms of different sacrificial ceremonies for the purification of the body, mind and intellect of an individual mankind. The Dharmasūtras proclaim that the religious purificatory rites and ceremonial activities are termed as the Saṁskāras. The *Gautamadharmasūtra*¹⁰ prescribe a list of altogether forty Saṁskāras, viz., *Puṁsavana*, *Sīmantonayana*, *Jātakarman*, *Nāmakaraṇa*, *Annaprāśana*, *Cuḍākaraṇa*, *Upanayana*, the four Vedavratas, *Snāna* or *Samāvartana*, *Vivāha*, five great sacrifices (viz., *Devayajña*, *Pitryajña*, *Manuṣyayajña*, *Bhūtayajña* and *Brahmayajña*), seven *Pākayajñas* (viz., *Aṣṭakā*, *Pārvaṇasthālīpāka*, *Śrāddha*, *Śrāvaṇī*, *Āgrahāyaṇī*, *Caitrī* and *Āśvayujī*), seven *Haviryajñas* (viz., *Agnyādheya*, *Agnihotra*, *Darśapurṇamāsa*, *Āgrayaṇa*, *Cāturmāsya*, *Nirūḍhapaśubandha* and *Sautrāmaṇī*), seven Soma sacrifices (viz., *Agniṣṭoma*, *Atyāgniṣṭoma*, *Ukthya*, *Ṣoḍaśī*, *Vājapeya*, *Atirātra* and *Aptoryāma*). Among these forty Saṁskāras, the combinations of the five-fold great sacrifices are called together as the *Pañcamahāyajñas*.¹¹

The *Gṛhasṭha* or householder must perform all domestic rites as well as the five great sacrifices; the five unavoidable day-to-day duties should be performed for life time. The great sacrifices, i.e. the *Pañcamahāyajñas* are explained clearly as the essential duty of the householder in the *Baudhāyanadharmasūtra*.¹² From the ancient Vedic times, the five great daily observances or the sacrifices were prescribed as the devotional acts and moral duties of a householder, chiefly a *Brāhmaṇa*.¹³

The *Śatapathabrāhmaṇa*¹⁴ and the *Taittirīyāranyaka*¹⁵ discuss about the *Pañcamahāyajñas* at length, while these five great sacrifices take a very important place in the *Gṛhyasūtras* and the *Dharmasūtras*. These *Pañcamahāyajñas* are viz., *Brahmayajña*, *Devayajña*, *Bhūtayajña*, *Pitryajña* and *Manuṣyayajña*. Usually, The *Brahmayajña* is the regular study and recitation of the Vedas. The offering of water to the forefathers is called the *Pitryajña*. The *Devayajña* is done by performing *Homa* to the gods. In the *Bhūtayajña*, a householder offers the oblations of food to the living beings, and lastly the hospitality and honour to men or guest is the *Manuṣyayajña* or *Nryajña*.

The *Vasiṣṭhadharmasūtra* illustrates about the *Pañcamahāyajñas* that, in the morning and evening a householder should offer a portion of cooked food in the fire as an oblation to all gods (*Devayajña*), make a *Bali* offering to the house-deities (*Bhūtayajña*), and after giving the portion to a Vedic scholar or student (*Brahmayajña*), immediately thereafter make an offering to his ancestors (*Pitryajña*) and then give some good food to the guest (*Atithiyajña*). After offerings to the gods and ancestors, a householder should give food to the guest and then after he and his wife should eat what remains.¹⁶

Moreover, the significance of each sacrifice is clearly depicted in the *Baudhāyanadharmasūtra*. From which, the importance of these simple but compulsory daily duties of all householders is observed. Every day a householder must offer even if it is just a piece of firewood with the ritual exclamation *Svāhā*, by which the Devayajña, i.e. the sacrifice to god is completed.¹⁷ By offering even if it is just a cup of water with the ritual exclamation *Svadhā* to his ancestors, a householder perform the Pitṛyajña.¹⁸ Every day the householder should pay homage to the beings even if it is just some flowers, by this way the *Bali* sacrifice or the Bhūtajajña is fulfilled.¹⁹ A householder should give food even if it is just some roots, fruits or vegetables to the *Brāhmaṇa* or guest as the sacrifice to the human or guest, i.e. the Manuṣyajajña or Atithyajajña.²⁰ Baudhāyana again says the Vedic recitation is the Brahmajajña. Everyday a householder should perform the recitation of the *Veda* even if it is just the syllable *aum*, the *praṇava* to fulfill the sacrifice to the *Brahman* or Vedic seer, i.e., the Brahmajajña.²¹

In the *Āpastambadharmasūtra*, the Pañcamahāyajñas are also explained in the same manner of the *Baudhāyanadharmasūtra* as follows- a householder should every day perform these by offering *Bali* to creatures (Bhūtajajña), giving food to men according to his capacity (Manuṣyajajña), offering at least one piece of wood to the fire as the oblation to the gods uttering the word *Svāhā* (Devayajña), make offer of at least a pot of water to the ancestors saying *Svadhā* (Pitṛyajña) and doing the recitation of the *Veda* (Brahmajajña). In simple word, householder should pay homage to gods, ancestors, humans, spirits and seers as his daily essential performances.²² The *Gautamadharmasūtra* has clearly mentioned that a householder should perform these five great sacrifices according to his best of capacity and ability.²³

The *Manusmṛti* also mentions these five great sacrifices as, viz., Ahuta, Huta, Prahuta, Brāhmya-huta and Prāśita. Here, the Ahuta is the muttering of the Vedic texts, i.e., the Brahmajajña. The Huta is the burnt oblations offered to the gods, i.e., the Devayajña. The Prahuta is the *Bali* offering given to the Bhūtas, i.e., the Bhūtajajña. The Brāhmya-huta is the respectful reception of a *Brāhmaṇa* or guests, i.e., the Manuṣyajajña, and the Prāśita is the daily oblations to the manes, also called the Tarpaṇa, i.e., the Pitṛyajña.²⁴

According to the great ancient Law-maker Manu, by the performance of these five great sacrifices, a householder is set free from different types of sins, committed through the use of *cullī*, a hearth; *peṣaṇa*, a grinding stone; *upaskara*, a broomstick; *kaṇḍanī*, a mortar and pestle; and *udakumbha*, a water pot.²⁵

The *Āpastambadharmasūtra* is said that the five great sacrifices are eulogized as the Mahāyajñas and the *Mahāsattrāṇi* or the great sacrificial sessions.²⁶ In this same approach P.V. Kane has explained about the Pañcamahāyajñas that these rites are called 'great sacrifices,' and 'great sacrificial sessions' by way of offering and glorification

only, the word *yajña* applied to these five daily duties is figurative and the adjective 'great' is applied only for be praising them.²⁷

INFLUENCE OF THE PERFORMANCE OF THE PAÑCAMAHĀYAJÑAS IN ASSAMESE SOCIETY

Assam is the frontier region in India on the North-East, which has had links with Aryan civilization and culture since the early period. The ancient names *Prāgjyotiṣapura* and *Kāmarūpa* of Assam are mentioned in ancient literature, particularly in the epics and the Purāṇas.²⁸ The entire North-Eastern region is the most culturally rich states of India. The socio-cultural tradition and ethnicity of a society represents the different aspects of that particular area. Culture is the set of rules to be acted by the common people that produce human behavior and activities. Thus, a human can exhibit his feelings towards the society as well as the creation. Culture is the man-made part of the environment.²⁹ The cultural syncretism of Assam is as remarkable as the whole Indian culture. The earliest residents of Assam were the Kiātas, Cīnas and other primitive tribes commonly designated as Mlecchas and Asuras.³⁰ There are many individual ethnic groups of people, viz. Baḍo, Rābhā, Kachārī, Micim, Gāro, Tivā, Kārbi, etc., have lived together in Assam as the Unity among diversity. Although Saivism and Saktism have had strong roots among the Assamese people, but Neo-Vaiṣṇavism was led with the spirit of liberation under the unique leadership of Mahāpuruṣa Śrī Śāṅkardeva (1449-1568), the great saint and scholarly personality of Assam. The influence of the Neo-Vaiṣṇavism on the Assamese people has since been prevalent, which have made the integration and assimilation between various tribal communities and Assamese Hindu society.³¹ In the Inscriptions from ancient Assam, the Kāmarūpa kings are frequently referred to as the protector of the *Varṇāśramadharmā*, the traditional divisions of society, viz., Brāhmaṇas, Kṣatriyas, Vaiśyas and Śūdras.³² After the fall of the royal power of the Gupta empire in the later part of the 5th century A.D. caused the migration of a large number of Brāhmaṇas to Kāmarūpa. And then, the Kāmarūpa kings patronage a large number of learned Scholars and religious teachers in the Kingdom by giving gifts of Land to pursue their religious sacrificial performances. The Brāhmaṇas of Kāmarūpa seem to have credited with living a holy and righteous life. They perform the daily rituals and duties. The first and foremost duty of a *Brāhmaṇa* was to pursue the study of the Vedas.³³ As the *Vasiṣṭhadharmasūtra* says that a *Brāhmaṇa* should always recite the Vedic text, here, the institution of the Brahmayajña or Svādhāya, one of the great duties of a householder, is achieved.³⁴ This practice of study the Vedic scriptures by the Brāhmaṇas is definitely added into the great instances about the influence of the Pañcamahāyajñas.

Although the clear influence of the Pañcamahāyajñas or the five great sacrificial performances are not entirely observed in Assamese society, some common traditional activities and practices seem to be linked with the Pañcamahāyajñas. The simple deeds

of the Pañcamahāyajñas have been performed by the householders of Assamese society in their daily life to some extent. As the tradition of Assamese culture, it is usually seen that, people used to offer their homage and respect to gods, scholarly persons, elders, guests and all other created living beings.

The Ancient Assamese scholars were well versed in the Vedic scriptures as well as in the Classical Epic-Books. Through the constant recitation and exposition of the Epics and Purāṇas, the teaching and learning process was traditionally developed in the Assamese culture. The Brahmajñas or Svādhyāya is observed in Assamese society as a culture of the Holy Book recitation, traditionally called *Puthi-Pātha*. Here, *Puthi* means the Holy Books and *Pātha* refers to reading out or recitation performance on the occasion of socio-religious activities. The *Bhāgavatapurāṇam*, the *Śrīmadbhagavadgītā*, the *Rāmāyaṇam*, the *Kīrttanaghoṣā* of Śankaradeva, the *Nāmaghoṣā* of Mādhavadeva, etc., are such type of Holy-Book, usually used to recite in various religious performances, which can be considered as the continuation of the practice of performing the Brahmajña in the ancient Indian society till contemporary period.

In the morning and evening, the Assamese family or a householder always devotes and offers the lighting oil lamp and the joss-stick in front of their Iṣṭadevatās, the Almighty and recites the *Harināma*, the devotional songs. The Devayajña is seen to be performed by the householders, till now, in the form of daily worship of gods and begging for the blessings and protection from the bad spirit and natural calamities. Generally, the Assamese Hindus believe and worship different gods and goddess, viz., Viṣṇu, Śiva, Gaṇeśa, Durgā, Lakṣmī, Manasā, Śītalā, etc.³⁵ Again, some people of Assamese society, specially the Brāhmaṇas perform the Vedic sacrifices, *Homa*, different kinds of domestic rites and rituals. They practice the religious institutions, according to the Vedic tradition of Gṛhyasūtras and Dharmasūtras till now. On the other hand, the followers of Śrī Śankaradeva used to sing the devotional songs called *Nāma-Prasaṅga* as the worship of the god. They strongly believe in one and only god as it is said- '*eka deva eka seva eka bine nai keva*'.

The influence of the Bhūtajña is still evident in the society. The offering of cooked food to the other living beings is usually observed among the Assamese people. The householder often offers the food and stuff to the domestic (cow, goat, dog, cat, pigeon, duck, cock, etc.) or non-domestic animals, birds, etc. As an agricultural society, the people of Assam used to rearing cattle. In the occasion of the *Garu Bihu*, the first day of the *Raṅgālī Bihu* in Assam, people treat the cows as divine goddesses Lakṣmī.³⁶ In this special day, the cows are taken to the nearby rivers or ponds to be bathed with very special care and treatment. As influenced by Bhūtajña, this is the best example observed in Assamese society. Again, although the elephant is not generally a domestic animal, but an elephant always be concerned as the incarnation of the god Gaṇeśa, the

god of welfare, by every householder in Assamese society. In his Holy Book Kīrttanagoṣā,³⁷ Śrīmanta Śankardeva says that the god exists in the souls of the animals like dogs, jackals, donkey, etc. So, we should honour or be kind to all living beings. Moreover, The *Vasiṣṭhadharmasūtra* also states that -a householder should be kind towards the entire creature and gives them food according to his ability.³⁸ Along with, the householder should throw some food on the ground for dogs, Cāṇḍālas, outcasts and crows.³⁹ Again, about the performance of the Bhūtayajña, the *Āpastambadharmasūtra* also says that the ground where the *Bali* offering is made should be purified.⁴⁰ In the society of Assam also, a householder is observed as he sweeps the area with his hand, sprinkling water on it, put down the offerings of food, and then sprinkles water all around.

From the Vedic age, the parents are honored as the god-- *pitṛdevo bhava*⁴¹ In Assamese cultural tradition, the householders from *Brāhmaṇa* family perform the annual *śrāddha* ceremony on the occasion of death anniversary of their departed parents or ancestors, as a mark of deep sense of gratitude, begging their blessings on them. Whereas, the *Āpastambadharmasūtra* has discussed about the daily ancestral offering, i.e., *Śrāddha*, that satisfy the ancestors.⁴² Again, in the occasion of *Bihu* and different ceremonials, Assamese people usually show their admiration and love to specially father, mother and all the elders by touching their feet as a sign of respect. This is obviously the accessible influence of the Pitṛyajña in the Assamese society. As the instance of the Pitṛyajña, the well-known ceremonial festivals, i.e., the *Medām-me-phi*, the *Chomāngkān*, etc., are celebrated by different Assamese ethnic groups.⁴³ The Tāi-Āhoms celebrate the death-rite known as *Medām-me-phi*, in which ceremony they offer the oblations to their ancestors and sacrifice to the gods. On the other hand, the Kārbis celebrate the death-rite with great festivity, called the *Chomāngkān*.

The service to man is the service to God, as the human body is the living temple of God. Irrespective of any caste and religion, it is the greatest service to a society. According to the *Vasiṣṭhadharmasūtra*, an *Atithi* or guest is called to a *Brāhmaṇa*, who spends one night and his stay is brief.⁴⁴ A householder should give to eat some goods and comfortable place to take rest, though the guest arrives in the evening.⁴⁵ In Assam, the guest or *Atithi* or *Ālahī* always feels free and comfortable as the family. Because of the kindheartedness and hospitality behavior of the different communities of Assam, the *Manuṣyayajña* or *Atithiyajña* is instituted naturally without any effort. It promotes the humanitarian aspect of the people of Assam, which brings the significant image in India and abroad. Every householder heartily does receive and welcome the guests and offers traditional Assamese food to the best of their capacity and ability. About the *Atithiyajña*, the *Gautamadharmasūtra* states that the *gṛhastha* should give the food at first to the guest, children, the sick, pregnant women, females in his household, the old person as well as the menials.⁴⁶ Likewise, in the Assamese society also, the

householder's wife has to take her meal in the end after giving to the other family members and cleaning the kitchen.⁴⁷

CONCLUSION

The Pañcamahāyajñas or five great sacrifices are significantly important and also the essential religious duties of a householder, which have more socio-religious, ethical and spiritual values. The Pañcamahāyajñas have been performed to the best of their capacities with small offerings and in simple ceremonies, which carries the enhancement of personality to the householder. Although the people of Assam do not maintain the regularity to perform the Pañcamahāyajñas, we can proudly say that the five great sacrifices are mostly practices as stated in the Dharmasūtras till now. The worshiping to the gods, showing respect and gratitude to the elders and forefathers, love and care for the living beings, hospitality to the guests or humanity for men and lastly the reading and learning of the Holy Books and scriptures – these five great performances teach us about the value of morality and the way to live a perfect life. These sacrifices always inspire the human society to develop and reform our cultural heritage as well as individual mind and soul.

References

1. cf., vedasya hastau kalpo'tha paṭhyate// *Pāṇinīyaśikṣā*, 41.
2. Vide., V.S. Apte. *The practical Sanskrit-English Dictionary*. Delhi: Motilal Banarsidass, 2007, p.855.
3. Ibid., p.1698.
4. Vide., P.V. Kane. *History of Dharmaśāstra*. Vol. I, Part 1. Poona : Bhandarkar Oriental Research Institute, 1974, p.9.
5. Vide., Ram Gopal. *India of Vedic Kalpasūtras*. Delhi : National Publishing House, 1959, p.45.
6. cf., athātaḥ sāmāyācārikāndharmānvyākhyāsyāmaḥ// *Āpastambadharmasūtra*, 1.1.
7. Vide., *Gautamadharmasūtra*, 19.1.
8. cf., a) brahmacārī gr̥hastho bhikṣurvaikhānasah// Ibid., 1.3.2.
b) brahmacārī gr̥hastho vānaprasthaḥ paribrājaka iti// *Baudhāyanadharmasūtra*, 2.11.12.
c) catvāra āśramāḥ// brahmacāriḥgr̥hasthavānaprasthaparibrājakāḥ// *Vasiṣṭhadharmasūtra*, 7.1-2.

9. cf., teṣāṃ gr̥hastho yoniraprajanatvāditareṣāṃ// *Gautamadharmasūtra*, 1.3.3.

10.cf.,garbhādhānapuṃsavanasīmantonayanajātakarmanāmakaraṇānnaprāśanacaulopa nayanam/ catvāri vedavratāni/ snānaṃ sahadharmacāriṇī-saṃyogaḥ/ pañcānāṃ yajñānāmanuṣṭhānaṃ devapitrmanuṣyabhūta-brahmaṇām/ eteṣāṃ ca/ aṣṭakā pūrvaṇaḥ śrāddhamśrāvanyāgrahāyaṇīm caityāśvayujīti sapta pākayajñasaṃsthāḥ/ agnyādheyamagnihotraṃ darśapūrṇamāsāvāgrayaṇam cāturmāsyaṇi nirūdhapaśubandhaḥ sautrāmaṇīti sapta haviryajñasaṃsthāḥ/ agniṣṭomo'tyagniṣṭomo, ukthyaḥ, ṣoḍaśī, vājapeyo'tirātro'ptoryāma iti sapta somasaṃsthāḥ/ ityete catvāriṃśatsaṃskārāḥ// *Ibid.*, 1.8.14-22.

11. cf., pañcānāṃ yajñānāmanuṣṭhānaṃ devapitrmanuṣyabhūta-brahmaṇām/ eteṣāṃ ca// *Ibid.*, 1.8.17-18.

12. cf., atheme pañca mahāyajñāḥ/ tānyeva mahāsatrāṇi/ devayajña pitryajño bhūtayajño manuṣyayajño brahmajajña iti// *Baudhāyanadharmasūtra*, 2.11.1.

13. cf., a) pātho homaścātithīnām saparyā tarpaṇam baliḥ/ ete pañca mahāyajñā brahmajajñādināmakāḥ// *Amarakośa*, 2.7.14.2.1.

b) The word *pañcamahāyajña* means 'the five daily sacrifices enjoined to be performed by a *Brāhmaṇa*.' Vide., V.S. Apte. *The practical Sanskrit-English Dictionary*. Delhi : Motilal Banarsidass, 2007, p.950.

c) The term *pañcamahāyajña* means 'the 5 great devotional acts of the Hindus.' Vide., M.M. Williams. *A Sanskrit-English Dictionary*. Delhi : Motilal Banarsidass, 2011, p.577.

14. pañcaiva mahāyajñāḥ / tānyeva mahāsatrāṇi bhūtayajño manuṣyayajñāḥ pitryajño devayajña brahmajajña iti // aharaḥbhūtebhyo balim haret/ tathaitam bhūtayajñam samāpnotyaraharadyādodapātrāttathaitam manuṣyayajñam samāpnotyaraharah svadhākuryādodapātrāttathaitam pitryajñam samāpnotyaraharah svadhākuryādā kāṣṭhāttathaitam devayajñam samāpnoti// *Śatapathabrāhmaṇa*, 11.5.6.1-2.

15. tatvidhiprasaṅgena pañcamahāyajñānvidhatte// pañca vā ete mahāyajñāḥ satati pratāyante satati saṃtiṣṭante devayajñāḥ pitryajño bhūtayajño manuṣyayajño brahmajajña iti / yadagno juhotyapi samidham taddevayajñāḥ saṃtiṣṭhate/ yat pitrbhyaḥ svadhā karotyapyapastatpitryajñāḥ saṃtiṣṭiate/ yadbhūtebho balim harati tad bhūtayajñāḥ saṃtiṣṭhate/ yad brāhmaṇebhyonnam dadāti tanmanuṣyayajñāḥ saṃtiṣṭhate/ yatsvādhyāyamadhīyātaikāmapyrcam yajuḥ sāma vā tad brahmajajñāḥ saṃtiṣṭhate// *Taittirīyāranyaka*, 2.10.

16. cf., śeṣam dampaṭī bhujñīyātām// *Vasiṣṭhadharmasūtra*, 11.11.
17. cf., aharahaḥ svāhākuryādākāṣṭhāt/ tathaitam devayajñam samāpnoti// *Baudhāyanadharmasūtra*, 2.11.2.
18. cf., aharahaḥ svadhākuryādodapātrāt/ tathaitam pitṛyajñam samāpnoti// *Ibid.*, 2.11.3.
19. cf., aharaharnamaskuryādāpuṣpebhyaḥ/ tathaitam bhūtayajñam samāpnoti// *Ibid.*, 2.11.4.
20. cf., aharaharbrāhmaṇebhyo'nnam dadyādāmūlaphalaśākebhyaḥ/ tathaitam manuṣyajñam samāpnoti// *Ibid.*, 2.11.5.
21. cf., aharahaḥ svādhyāyam kuryādapraṇavāt/ tathaitam brahmayajñam samāpnoti// *Ibid.*, 2.11.6.
22. a) devapitṛmanuṣyabhūtarṣipūjakaḥ/ nityasvādhyāyaḥ/ pitṛbhyaścodakadānam// *Ibid.*, 5.3-5.
b) devapitṛmanuṣyayajñāḥ svādhyāyaśca balikarama, *Gautamadharmasūtra*, 5.9.
23. cf., yathotsāhamanyat// *Ibid.*, 5.6.
24. a) adhyāpanam brahmayajñāḥ pitṛyajñastu tarpaṇam/
homo daiva balirbhuto nṛyajño' tithipūjanam// *Manusmṛti*, 3.70.
b) ahutañca hutañcaiva tathā prahutameva ca/
brāhmyam hutam prāśitañca pañca yajñān pracakṣate//
japo'huto huto homaḥ prahuto bautiko baliḥ/
brāhmyam hutam dvijāgryārcā prāśitam pitṛtarpaṇam// *Ibid.*, 73-74.
25. pañcasūnā cullī peṣaṇyupaskaraḥ/ kaṇḍanī codakumbhaśca vadhyate yāstu
vāhayet // tāsām krameṇa sarvāsām niskṛtyartham maharṣibhiḥ/ pañca klṛptā
mahāyajñāḥ pratyaham gṛhamedhinām// *Ibid.*, 3.68.
- 26.a) teṣām mahāyajñā mahāsattrāṇīti sanstutiḥ// aharaharbhūtabalirmanuṣyebhyo
yathāśaktidānam// *Āpastambadharmasūtra*, 1.12.14-15.
b) devebhyaḥ svāhākāra ā kāṣṭhātpitṛbhyaḥ svadhākāra odapātrātsvādhyāya iti// *Ibid.*,
1.13.1.
27. a) cf., *Āśvalāyanagrhyasūtra*, III.1.2.
b) Vide., P.V. Kane. *The History of Dharmasūtra*. Vol. II, Part I, Poona : Bhandarkar
Oriental Research Institute, p.697, foot note 1666.

- 28 Vide., B.K. Barua. *A Cultural History of Assam*, Vol. I, Guwahati : Bina Library, 1951, p. 9-12.
29. Vide., Melville J. Herskovits. *Cultural Anthropology*. New Delhi, 1974, p.305.
30. Vide., B.K. Barua. *A Cultural History of Assam*, Vol. I. Guwahati : Bina Library, 1951, p. 04.
31. Vide., Birendranath Datta (ed.). *A Handbook of Folklore Material of North-East India*. Guwahati : Anundoram Borooh Institute of Language, Art & Culture, 1994, p. 4.
32. Vide., B.K. Barua. *A Cultural History of Assam* Vol. I. Guwahati : Bina Library, 1951, p.103.
33. Ibid., p.104-109.
34. cf., nityasvādhyāyī// *Vasiṣṭhadharmasūtra*, 8.17.
35. Vide., Birendranath Datta (ed.). *A Handbook of Folklore Material of North-East India*. Guwahati : Anundoram Borooh Institute of Language, Art & Culture, 1994, p.116-117.
36. Vide., Nirmalprabha Bordoloi. *Asamar Loka Sanskrit*. Guwahati : Bina Library, 2008, p.33.
37. Vide., *Kīrttanagoṣā*, 4.1823.
38. cf., yathāśakti cānna sarvabhūtāni// *Vasiṣṭhadharmasūtra*, 8.13.
39. cf., śvacāṇḍālapatitavāyasebhyo bhūmau nirvapet// Ibid., 11.9.
40. cf., balīnām tasya tasya deśe saṅskāro hastena parimṛjyāvokṣya nyupya paścātpariṣecanam// *Āpastambadharmasūtra*, 2.3.15.
41. *Taittirīyopaniṣad*, 1.11.2.
42. cf., nityaśrāddham/ *Āpastambadharmasūtra*, 2.18.5.
43. Vide., Birendranath Datta (ed.). *A Handbook of Folklore Material of North-East India*. Guwahati : Anundoram Borooh Institute of Language, Art & Culture, 1994, p. 169-171.

44. cf., ekarātrm tu nivasannatithirbrāhmaṇaḥ smṛtaḥ/ anityam hi sthito yasmāttasmādatithirucyate// *Vasiṣṭhadharmasūtra*, 8.7.

45. cf., sāyamāgatamatithim nāparundhyāt// *Ibid.*, 8.4.

46.cf.,bhojayetpūrvamatithikumāravayādhitagarbhiṅṣuvāsinīsthavirāñjaghanyāmñca// *Gautamadharmasūtra*, 5.25.

47. Vide., Nirmalprabha Bordoloi. *Asamar Loka Sanskrit*. Guwahati : Bina Library, 2008, p.41.

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